

A novel thiourea-based colorimetric chemosensor for sensitive and selective detection of sulphate ion in semi-aqueous medium

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Abstract : Within the pool of naturally available anions, the sulphate anion has gained a certain level of notoriety by playing a critical role in contaminating the animal food chain, apart from disturbing marine life via paralysis of certain ecological cycles. Under such circumstances, it becomes imperative to regulate the influx of this potentially hazardous anion into the ecosystem. An important section of the remediation strategies in this area would involve an efficient sensing and quantification of this toxic anion, particularly in the natural water systems. In continuation of our efforts to exploit the unique photophysical properties of ligand-tagged nanoparticles to achieve selective ion-recognition potential, this report highlights the chemical synthesis and chemosensing efficacy of a new and selective sulphate-recognising organic receptor OR in aqueous medium. Upon decoration of OR onto ZnO nanoparticles, the nanohybrid OR@ZnO demonstrated a rapid response and selectivity towards the hydrogen sulphate anion, as marked by a significant alteration in the absorbance and fluorescence profile of OR@ZnO in aqueous system with a significantly low limit of detection (100 nM).

Keywords : ZnO, surface decoration, sulphate, thiourea, fluorescence, sensor.

Introduction

Inorganic sulphates are naturally available in several minerals, including barite (BaSO₄), epsomite (MgSO₄·7H₂O) and gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O)¹. Amongst the several non-transition metal sulphates, sodium, potassium and magnesium sulphates are all highly soluble in water whereas many heavy metal sulphates (like barium sulfate) are less soluble. In addition to a plethora of industrial applications, inorganic sulphates also harbor potential biological relevance at physiological concentrations². For instance, the sulphate moiety constitutes an integral part of several polysaccharides (found in animal tissues) like heparin sulphate, which upon binding to a variety of protein ligands, regulates biological processes like cell signaling, angiogenesis and regulation of enzyme activity³. In the recent decades

and as a consequence of the industrial revolution, a meteoric rise in the concentration of the inorganic sulphate ion in natural aquatic systems has been broadly attributed to acid rain, non-regulated use of sulphate-containing fertilizers and oxidation of pyrite deposits in the subsoil⁴. A serious consequence of an overload of this otherwise harmless sulphate ion is the aberrant increase in phosphorus levels in the aquatic system, leading to an uncontrolled growth of certain algae and lower oxygen levels in the water systems. Such a phenomenon, known as eutrophication, poses a serious ecological hazard to marine life⁵. In addition, another phytotoxic effect of sulphate-overdose has been increasingly realised in the form of an excess generation and accumulation of methyl mercury in the deep waters⁶⁻⁸. Therefore, in due recognition of the ubiquitous nature

of the sulphate anion and a unique sulphatemethyl mercury relationship, it is imperative to recognise and quantify sulphate concentrations in the natural water bodies in order to promote potential remediation strategies for specifically limiting the production and accumulation of MeHg in the sediment pore-water.

In an attempt to do so, there has been a growing interest in developing highly selective chemical receptors to facilitate a facile and selective recognition and quantification of the sulphate ion in water systems⁹. In contrast to a broad spectrum of metal ion-sensors, several reports in the past have harboured a certain bias towards positively-charged/metal-containing chemical receptors as a favourite class for anion detection in aqueous medium^{10,11}. Interestingly, certain natural anion-binding systems exhibit high affinity and selectivity for certain substrates under physiological conditions, apparently upon shielding of the latter from neighbouring solvent molecules via recognition into a cleft or cavity of the folded polypeptide chains. For example, sulphate binding proteins (SBP) responsible for anion transport in bacteria bind sulphate exceptionally well in water via hydrogen bonding¹². However, some critical factors that may impede the binding of sulphate anion to neutral receptors in aqueous systems include the former's relatively high hydration energy, thereby making the anion strongly hydrophilic and difficult to detect in aqueous phase¹³. Such challenges encountered in the detection of sulphate-anion in aqueous systems have been often cited in scientific literature. For example, despite a high selectivity for sulphate anion in organic solvent medium, Shao *et al.* demonstrated a limited environmental applicability of their novel indole-based chemosensor in aqueous medium¹⁴. Molina *et al.* have also postulated a similar trend by demonstrating a measurable sulphate-recognizing potential of a ferrocene-incorporated chemoreceptor in acidic medium, whose sensitivity, however, diminishes drastically in a neutral medium¹⁵. In the above and certain other related studies, the sulphate-sensing ability of potential chemoreceptors has been proposed to heavily rely on protonation of the host

receptors, followed by a subsequent anion coordination within the receptor cleft via H-bonding and electrostatic interactions¹⁶. Therefore, a rational incorporation of specific sulphate-binding chemical moieties into a suitable neutral host would be ideal for selective recognition of a sulphate anion in aqueous medium, thereby circumventing the need for protonation of the receptor ligand, prior to sulphate detection.

In this regard, several urea/thiourea-based host ligands are amongst the most successful group of neutral chemical receptors for recognising sulphate ion in a highly competitive aqueous medium^{10,17}. This may be attributed to a facile hydrogen-bonding interaction between the acidic H-bond donor moiety (NH of host ligand) and sulphate anion (guest), thereby ensuring a sensitive chemical affinity between the two species¹⁸. Upon an evaluation of previously reported sulphate-sensing chemosensors, a major concern regarding their environmental relevance lies in their efficacy in physiological medium and their limit of sensitivity.

In due recognition of the same and our long-standing interest in finely tunable ion-recognition properties of biocompatible ZnO nanoparticles, we have exploited this unique "amine-sulphate chemistry" in the chemical synthesis of a novel **OR@ZnO** nano hybrid¹⁹. The subsequent modulatory effects of this nanosensor, resulting in a sensitive and selective recognition of a physiologically relevant sulphate-ion, has been discussed henceforth.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of organic receptor (OR) : The rationale of this investigation is to obtain the selectivity of a chemical receptor towards a specific anionic guest; which is being governed through multiple interactions between host and guest in a complementary fashion^{20,21}. The work is themed on the fact that synthetic receptors with flexible arms possess a shape complementary to tetrahedral anions because the geometry and orientation of the host molecule favour the formation of stable host-guest complexes²². This concept has been corroborated with the

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excellent work of Wu *et al.*; which highlighted the exceptional sulphate-binding properties of a novel tripod-like hexaurea through the encapsulation of the tetrahedral anion with six urea groups involving multiple hydrogen bonds²³. The reported chemical sensors involve multiple steps and tedious purification techniques for the synthesis of such functional organic receptors¹⁸. However, the organic receptor projected in our work **OR** was synthesized by a relatively shorter and facile protocol. The **OR** was furnished as a yellow solid in quantitative yield (86% overall) through the nucleophilic addition of a commercially available derivative of isothiocyanate to a secondary amine (Fig. 1A). The latter, in turn, was easily synthesized by sodium-borohydride-mediated reduction of a Schiff base which was synthesized by a one-step condensation reaction between commercially available salicylaldehyde and *n*-propyl amine in water-free methanol¹⁸. Purity of the title ligand **L** was confirmed by its detailed physico-chemical characterization using IR, ¹H/¹³C NMR and electrospray ionisation (ESI) mass spectroscopy in addition to elemental analysis. In accordance with the results obtained from the IR spectrum, an observation of a distinct stretching frequency band at 1621 cm⁻¹, which is characteristic of an imine-linked (-CH=N) functional group, provided evidence of the formation of the final product **L**. As per the result obtained from NMR spectroscopy, the peak corresponding to the

iminic functionality (-CH=N) at 7.27 ppm and at 165.9 ppm in the ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR, respectively, confirmed the complete consumption of the reactant, 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde²⁴. In addition, an upfield shift in the NMR signal (3.7 ppm) corresponding to the CH₂-N protons of **L**, relative to a rather deshielded environment around its precursor proton in benzaldehyde (10.64 ppm) can be related to the lower electronegativity of a nitrogen atom (as in **L**).

In order to identify the mass spectrum of the receptor ligand **L** on the basis of its mass/charge (*m/z*) ratio, a solution of the same was subjected to ionisation via electrospray technique²⁵. The appearance of an intense molecular ion peak (at 346.1) confirmed the presence of a protonated adduct of **OR**. A close difference in the observed and calculated percentage of the individual elements in **OR** further confirmed its purity in bulk.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 9.93 (1H, br, -OH), 9.72 (1H, s, -NH), 8.1 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.6 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.13 (2H, m, -CH₂), 6.86 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.81 (1H, t, Ar-H), 4.9 (2H, s, Ar-CH₂), 3.7 (2H, t, -N-CH₂) and 0.86 (3H, t, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 178.34, 154.90, 152.28, 149.82, 147.80, 142.22, 128.35, 123.75, 123.25, 119.12, 115.08, 39.70, 39.28, 39.08 and 11.01; ESI-MS *m/z* = 346.1 [M+H]⁺; CHN analysis Calcd. for

Fig. 1. (A) Chemical structure of organic receptor (**OR**) depicting the signal subunit; potential binding sites for anion recognition and moieties to anchor the receptor (**OR**) over the ZnO; (B) Possible binding mode of organic receptor (**OR**) over the surface of ZnO and projecting the H-bonding sites for anion recognition.

$C_{21}H_{22}N_2OS$: C, 59.11; H, 5.54; N, 12.16. Found : C, 59.77; H, 5.88; N, 12.51.

Surface decoration of ZnO with organic receptor (OR) and characterization of OR@ZnO

ZnO is a wide band gap semiconductor, possessing high exciton binding energy with a stable Wurtzite structure. It has attracted exhaustive efforts into an elucidation of its unique applications in antireflection coatings, solar cells, diode lasers and antibacterial properties²⁶. Nowadays, ZnO nanoparticles, in conjugation with a plethora of organic and bio-chemical ligands are being popularly utilized as a potential ion-sensing candidate due to their immense selectivity and sensitivity. A significant biocompatibility and highly adjustable photophysical properties in the presence of the ion-of-interest renders ZnO nanoparticles as a desirable analytical probe²⁷. In an attempt to explore a potential ion-sensing capability of a new thiourea-based aromatic derivative **OR** the new organic receptor was further decorated onto ZnO nanoaggregates in order to achieve a stable analytical sensor system in aqueous medium^{28,29}. Details of the procedure for synthesis of **OR**-linked ZnO nanoparticles include mixing an alcoholic solution of $Zn(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (595 mg, 2.0 mmol) and an alcoholic solution of NaOH (120 mg, 3.0 mmol). A white product was separated out and the product was washed and dried at 150 °C. Compound **OR** (804 mg, 3 mmol) was mixed with freshly prepared ZnO nanoparticles (100 mg) under constant stirring at 25 °C in dry $CHCl_3$ and the solution was refluxed for 15 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored with IR and UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. Upon completion of reaction, the final product was isolated by centrifugation and washed successively with ethanol and water. The procured product **OR@ZnO** was dried for 24 h at 50 °C. The size, morphology, chemical composition and spectroscopic features of the receptor-capped Zn nanoparticles were elucidated by XRD, SEM, EDAX, solid state UV-Vis and fluorescence studies, respectively. The particle size distribution of the receptor-decorated ZnO nanoparticles was estimated

by dynamic light scattering (DLS) studies using a probe based Metrohm microtrac Ultra nanotracer particle size analyzer. The SEM image depicts that modified ZnO nanoparticles form supramolecular self-assembled morphology with growth limited in particular directions and thereby generating tripodal geometry (Fig. 2A). The EDAX analysis of **OR@ZnO** points towards the simultaneous presence of zinc, oxygen and carbon, thereby distinctly confirming a coating of the organic receptor **OR** onto the surface of ZnO (Fig. 2B). The thickness of **OR**-capped ZnO nanoparticles (**OR@ZnO**) was characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS), which estimates the hydrodynamic diameter of **OR@ZnO** to be 560 nm (Fig. 2C). Herein, variation in the particle size measured by SEM (200 nm, in this case) and DLS was observed. This can be attributed to the fact that SEM only estimates the size of the particle core neglecting the surrounding solvent layer. In contrast, DLS studies measures the size of the solvent-adhering particles under the influence of brownian motion, thereby making it a more reliable technique in comprehending and optimizing the nanoparticles' performance in analytical and biological assays. In contrast, SEM estimates the size of the particles without the hydration layer and is a more reliable technique to measure the size of coated nanoparticles²⁶. The solid state UV-Vis absorption spectra of pure ZnO exhibit a peak at 360 nm corresponding to the exciton state of ZnO (Fig. 2D, Supporting Information)²⁹. The λ_{max} of the absorption spectra of **OR@ZnO** was blue-shifted as compared to that of pure ZnO (Fig. 2D). The solid-state photoluminescence spectrum of **OR@ZnO**, which was recorded at an excitation wavelength of 325 nm, displayed an intense peak at 330 nm and 456 nm (as of pure ZnO) (Fig. 2E); however, the intensity of a characteristic green band at 570 nm (corresponding to pure ZnO) quenched in case of **OR@ZnO**. According to Dijken's postulate, the visible emission band can be attributed to the formation of a recombination center (V_o^{**}), where the valence band hole is trapped onto the surface, which then tunnels back into the oxygen holes

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containing one electron (V_o^*)²⁷. This recombination of a shallow trapped electron with a deeply trapped hole in a V_o^{**} center is responsible for visible emission, thereby explaining the role of multiple surface defects in pure ZnO as a probable cause leading to intense emissions in the visible region. Such defects at the grain boundaries of ZnO may enable a probable conjugation with -OH and -CH=N groups of **OR**, thereby resulting in a decrease in interfacial defects in **OR**-capped ZnO and a consequent lowering in green region emission (Fig. 2E). Finally, X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the prepared **OR@ZnO** nanopowder, calcined at 500 °C was also recorded (Fig. 2F), depicting scattering angles (2θ) of 31.79, 34.40, 36.25, 47.56, 56.56, 62.82 and 67.91, corresponding to reflections from 100, 002, 101, 102, 110, 103 and 112 planes of the crystal, respectively. All diffraction peaks are in good agreement with literature reports, which

can be indexed as the hexagonal Wurtzite structure of ZnO with lattice constants of $a = 3.253 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.207 \text{ \AA}$. No other peak (except assigned for ZnO) was visualized, thereby confirming the purity of the sample. In accordance with Debye-Scherrer's equation ($D = 0.89\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$), where λ is the wavelength of incident X-ray (0.15418 nm), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of diffraction peak and θ is the diffraction angle, the average crystalline size of the ZnO nanocrystals was estimated to be 30.55 nm.

Anion recognition properties of OR@ZnO : The title ligand **OR** belongs to a class of thiourea-based derivatives (Fig. 1A). As discussed earlier, such type of compounds possess multiple NH (as hydrogen bond donor) functionalities, therefore being able to demonstrate ion-sensing potential receptors by facilitating anion coordination through multiple hydrogen bonding^{13,14}. However, due to the rather high hydrophili-

Fig. 2. (A) SEM image of **OR@ZnO**, displaying a self-assembled morphology due to its structure directing nature; (B) EDXA of **OR@ZnO** depicting the presence of zinc and oxygen along with carbon, thereby confirming the capping of organic ligand **OR** onto ZnO nanoparticles; (C) Size distribution analysis of **OR@ZnO** (representing a hydrodynamic diameter of 560 nm); (D) Solid-state UV-Vis absorbance profile of **OR@ZnO**; (E) Solid-state fluorescence emission spectra of **OR@ZnO** (upon excitation at 320 nm); (F) X-Ray powder diffractogram of **OR@ZnO** (average crystallite size of **OR@ZnO** estimated to be 30 nm).

city of biologically relevant anions, a chemical recognition and quantification of such ionic species has posed a major challenge in aqueous phase¹². This, in turn, has been attributed to the water-mediated disruption of H-bonding and/or electrostatic interactions between the ion of interest and host species³⁰. In order to explore a probable chemical affinity of **OR@ZnO** towards a pool of tetrabutyl ammonium salts of physiologically relevant anions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CN^- , CH_3COO^- , HSO_4^- , PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- and ClO_4^-), its photophysical properties were inspected by UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy in HEPES buffered acetonitrile/ H_2O (98 : 2) system. Accordingly, due to the presence of an arene-conjugated thiocarbonyl moiety, the native absorption spectrum of **OR@ZnO** exhibited an intense absorption band (at 450 nm) in the near UV region (Fig. 3A). This characteristic peak is primarily attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions resulting from an electron dipole movement, commonly observed in aromatic carbonyl compounds³¹. Further, upon an addition of small aliquots of a solution of each tetrabutyl ammonium anion salt (5 equivalents) to a solution of **OR@ZnO**, the absorption profile of **OR@ZnO** experienced a distinct hypochromic shift and a slight bathochromic shift in the receptor's charge transfer band (460 nm) only in the vicinity of hydrogen sulphate anion. This could apparently be attributed to certain alterations in the electronic levels (HOMO/LUMO) of **OR@ZnO**, upon coordination to the electron-rich hydrogen sulphate anion³². In addition, the absorption spectrum of native **OR@ZnO** displayed an uphill slope from 380–465 nm, in contrast to a downhill slope observed in the same region in the vicinity of hydrogen sulphate ion. A similar trend was, however, not observed in the presence of other anions which indicated towards a certain physico-chemical sensitivity of **OR@ZnO** towards the hydrogen sulphate anion.

On the other hand, **OR@ZnO** nanoaggregates did not experience any marked alterations in its UV-Vis absorption spectrum in the presence of any of the select metal ions, thereby pointing towards an inherent inability of the metal cations in altering the electronic

environment of the chemical sensor in its ground state. In order to corroborate the selective binding of **OR@ZnO** with HSO_4^- in aqueous medium, titration studies were carried out. Accordingly, upon a successive addition of HSO_4^- (0–80 μM) to a solution of the chemoreceptor **OR@ZnO** in aqueous medium, a distinct drop in the intensity of its native absorption peak at 455 nm was observed with a concomitant formation of a new peak at 360 nm (Fig. 3B). In consequence, a clear isobestic point was observed at 390 nm, indicating the formation of a well-defined **OR@ZnO- HSO_4^-** scaffold (Fig. 3B). The titration experiment indicated a considerable linearity (98%) within a concentration range of 0 μM to 50 μM (Fig. 3C). Using these titration data, the nanoaggregates **OR@ZnO** were found to detect HSO_4^- ions in aqueous phase upto 100 nM (3σ method)³³. Upon an introspection of the library of potentially novel HSO_4^- -sensing chemosensors proposed in the past, the ultra-sensitivity of **OR@ZnO** matches closely to one of our recently reported and highly sensitive HSO_4^- -detecting chemosensor^{10,33}. Such a significantly low detection limit is encouraging enough to introduce this newly synthesized receptor into the elite class of environmentally relevant and highly selective HSO_4^- -sensing chemosensors. To summarize, this titration experiment confirmed a selective and sensitive affinity of **OR@ZnO** towards HSO_4^- ion in aqueous medium. In order to further validate the on-field applicability and selective chemical affinity of **OR@ZnO** towards HSO_4^- in a competitive aqueous medium, an interference experiment was carried out by subjecting a solution of **OR@ZnO** to HSO_4^- and a pool of select interfering anions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CN^- , CH_3COO^- , PO_4^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^-), simultaneously. In accordance with the results obtained, there was an insignificant variation in the absorbance profile of HSO_4^- -tagged **OR@ZnO** in the presence of the competing anions (Fig. 3D). Therefore, it could be deduced that **OR@ZnO** selectively coordinates with HSO_4^- irrespective of the presence of other competing anions.

The physico-chemical stability of ligand-capped

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Fig. 3. Variation in UV-Vis absorption profile of **OR@ZnO** in HEPES buffered acetonitrile/water (98 : 2 v/v) solvent system : (A) In presence of test anions; (B) Upon successive addition of sulphate anion (0–80 μM); (C) Linear regression plot between concentration of sulphate ion added (0–50 μM) and change in absorbance of **OR@ZnO** with a linear regression coefficient of 0.9779; (D) Competitive binding studies of **OR@ZnO** nanoaggregates (1) towards sulphate anion (2) in the presence of other interfering anions : F^- (3), Cl^- (4), Br^- (5), I^- (6), CN^- (7), CH_3COO^- (8), PO_4^- (9), NO_3^- (10) and ClO_4^- (11).

nanoparticles are influenced by their local environment. Presence of electrolyte ions in the immediate vicinity may influence the charge on the nanoparticle surface (basically in first order by the Debye-Hückel effect), thereby resulting in electrochemical instability and consequent agglomeration³⁴. A similar degradative effect on the aggregation state of nanoparticles may also be exerted by a pH-mediated protonation/deprotonation of acidic groups on surface of ligand-coated nanoparticles. As a consequence, such environmental factors serve as critical parameters in governing the stability and ion-sensing relevance of

fluorophore-labelled NPs under water. In order to identify an appropriate pH range in which nanoaggregates can selectively probe HSO_4^- , acid/base titrations were carried out. The absorbance of the title ligand-coated ZnO nanoaggregates **OR@ZnO** was observed to vary negligibly within a pH range of 2.7 to 11.2 (Fig. 4A). To conclude, a change in pH over a broad range apparently exerted a minimal effect on the physico-chemical stability of the nanoaggregates of **R1**. The effect of ionic strength on the ion-sensing potential of the nanoaggregates **OR@ZnO** was investigated by comparing the absorbance spectrum of native **OR@ZnO**

(0.5 μM) with the absorbance spectrum obtained upon addition of 0–100 equiv. of the tetrabutyl ammonium (TBA) salt of perchlorate to **OR@ZnO** (Fig. 4B)³³. In accordance with the procured data, there was a negligible variation in the absorbance curves, thereby indicating that even an excessive addition of salts yields a marginal effect on the ion-sensing ability of the nanoaggregates **OR@ZnO**. In order to investigate the response time of **OR@ZnO** towards HSO_4^- , the absorbance spectrum of the same was recorded in the absence and presence of different concentrations of HSO_4^- (15, 30, 50 μM) and analyzed as a function of time. In accordance with the data obtained (Fig. 4C), the absorbance of **OR@ZnO** corresponding to the select concentrations of HSO_4^- did not vary after 35 seconds of start of the experiment. In other words, the

response period of **OR@ZnO** towards HSO_4^- was found to be less than 35 s.

Proposed mechanistic pathway for selective binding of receptor N1 to sulphate anion

There is ample scientific evidence which confirms the critical reliance of certain biological sulphate-ion transporters on hydrogen bonding for the selective binding and transport of this hydrophilic anion across the cellular membrane¹¹. For instance, an elucidation of the X-ray structure of the sulphate-binding site in a specific sulphate-binding protein reveals the encapsulation of the anion in a peptide pocket via H-bonding with the N-H and O-H groups of the protein. In addition, ion-sensing studies and structural data of the sulphate-engulfed single crystals of a plethora of syn-

Fig. 4. (A) Effect of pH on stability of **OR@ZnO** nanoaggregates in aqueous medium; (B) Salt perturbation studies of ion-sensing **OR@ZnO** nanoaggregates in aqueous medium upon addition of $(\text{Bu})_4\text{N}^+\text{ClO}_4^-$ (0–100 equiv.); (C) Time-dependent response of **OR@ZnO** towards varying concentrations of HSO_4^- (15, 30, 50 μM).

thetic urea-based receptors further validate the significant role of H-bonding interactions in the sulphate-recognizing ability of chemical receptors with a common amide/thioamide containing structural motif^{10,11}. In due consideration of the same, a probable mode of sensing of sulphate ion by the title thiourea-based ligand **1B**, via a potential H-bonding interaction with the acidic H-bond donor moiety (NH and OH) of the receptor ligand has been postulated.

Conclusion

A diverse library of potential chemical sensors against the physiologically relevant sulphate anion have been proposed in the past³⁴⁻³⁷. However, a limited water solubility and relatively low sensitivity continue to restrict their applicability in the immediate environment. In due consideration of the same, we propose a new thiourea-based ligand **OR** as a potentially novel sulphate ion-sensing ligand. The new thiourea-based receptor **OR** was quantitatively synthesized by the nucleophilic addition of a secondary amine to a phenyl isothiocyanate derivative under ambient reaction conditions. Upon capping onto environmentally compatible ZnO nanoparticles, the novel nanohybrid **OR@ZnO** demonstrated a distinct chemical sensitivity and selectivity towards sulphate anion over other biologically relevant ions in aqueous medium, with a significantly low detection limit of 100 nM. This potentially novel sulphate sensor may find industrial applicability in the global fight against sulphate-induced water pollution.

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